

ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP AND INNOVATION IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION: THE MEDIATING IMPACT OF WORK ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study aims to analyze the effect of proactive personality and entrepreneurial leadership on innovative work behavior mediated by work engagement in state civil apparatus at the cooperative service in West Sumatera. The type of research uses explanatory research. While the research approach uses an explanatory survey that emphasizes quantitative research methods. The entire population Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatera totaling 664 people, with a sample size of 250 people. The sampling technique used proportionate stratified random sampling. Data analysis using Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). The mediation testing strategy uses the path coefficient significance. The results of the study found proactive Personality has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. Proactive Personality has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior. Work engagement has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior. Entrepreneurial Leadership has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. Entrepreneurial Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior. Work engagement mediates the influence of Proactive Personality and Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with the form of mediation is complementary mediation in the form of partial mediation</p>	<p>Proactive Personality, Entrepreneurial Leadership, Work Engagement, Innovative Work Behavior</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are an important aspect that must exist in an organization (Sari et al., 2023) Human resources are required to be able to see opportunities, take initiative, take action, and be persistent in facing changes that occur in the organization (Kebede & Wang, 2022). In today's increasingly rapid development, human resources are required to be creative and innovative in order to achieve the progress of their organization (Sari et al., 2023). Innovation is a very important factor for organizations because organizations are required to be able to adapt to rapid environmental changes (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017). In carrying out an innovation, employees involved in its creation are expected to be able to pour out new ideas to achieve organizational goals. Therefore, employee innovative behavior needs to be developed (Prieto & Pérez-Santana, 2014).

Innovative work behavior relates to the development, adoption, and implementation of new ideas for products, technologies, and work methods by employees; it is considered a critical determinant of an organization's success. Innovative Work Behavior is critical to the effectiveness and viability of an organization, ultimately leading to sustainable organizational development. Innovative Work Behavior must be carried out continuously by organizations, both profit-oriented and non-profit organizations. One of the non-profit organizations that must also implement Innovative Work Behavior is a public organization. Public organizations are characterized by various procedures and regulations that provide a high level of control and a low level of flexibility (Srirahayu et al., 2023).

One of the public organizations is a government organization or agency. Government agencies are filled with human resources as the driving force of the organization. State Civil Apparatus or also abbreviated as ASN is one example of employees or staff in an organization and government agency. ASN employees are classified as Civil Servants and Government Employees with Work Agreements, who are appointed by personnel development officials and given tasks in a government position or given other state tasks and are paid based on laws and regulations. Srirahayu et al., (2023) states the unique innovation demands on government employees regarding the use of resources to create innovative results.

The State Civil Apparatus itself is spread across every government agency starting from the Central Government, Provincial Government to Regency and City Government, as well as in the Cooperative Services in the government areas in West Sumatra Province. Where the Cooperative Services in the Regency and City in the West Sumatra Province have the obligation and responsibility to carry out coaching, empowerment and protection, supervision and inspection of Cooperatives in West Sumatra Province. In order to carry out its obligations, the Cooperative Service is supported by Human Resources in the form of State Civil Apparatus who work in the agency,

One of the evaluations of the performance assessment of the Cooperative Service agency can be seen from the number of active Cooperatives and Cooperatives that hold Annual Member Meetings each year. Law No. 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives states that the implementation of the Annual Members Meeting is an obligation of every cooperative as a form of accountability of the management and supervisors to all cooperative members. The following is the percentage achievement of the number of active Cooperatives and Cooperatives that have implemented the Annual Members Meeting in the last 5 (five) years can be seen in the following table.

Table 1 Data on Active Cooperatives and Cooperatives that are implementing Annual Members Meeting in West Sumatra.

Data on Active Cooperatives and Cooperatives Implementing Annual Members Meeting In West Sumatera Province

Cooperatives that Annual Members

Fiscal Year	Total Number	of Active Cooperative Meeting			
		Unit	%	Unit	%
2018	3.624	2.815	77.7%	1,404	38.7%
2019	3.805	2,969	78.0%	1,566	41.2%
2020	3.981	2.004	50.3%	1.205	30.3%
2021	4.048	1,981	48.9%	1.213	30.0%

2022	4.137	2,090	50.5%	1.217	29.4%
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Period Cooperatives (units)

Source: Cooperatives and SMEs Service of West Sumatra Province, January 2024

From table 1 it can be explained that when viewed from the total number of cooperatives, the number of cooperatives has increased every year from the 2018 financial year to the 2022 financial year. However, despite the increase in terms of the number of cooperatives, there is a tendency for a decrease in the percentage of active cooperatives and a tendency for a decrease in cooperatives holding Annual Member Meetings. The tendency for a decrease in active cooperatives and cooperatives holding Annual Member Meetings can be said that there is an indication that the West Sumatra Cooperative Service has not yet succeeded in achieving its goals and also shows an indication that the organization has not been fully supported by individual human resources who have Innovative Work Behavior to produce, promote, and realize new ideas in fostering and encouraging Cooperatives to be able to hold Annual Member Meetings and become active.

In the scope of the State Civil Apparatus, Innovative Work Behavior is a form of implementation of one of the basic values that apply to the State Civil Apparatus known as the Core Values of ASN BERAKHLAK which is an acronym for Service Oriented, Accountable, Competent, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, Collaborative, where in the Adaptive section the State Civil Apparatus are required to continue to innovate and be enthusiastic in driving and facing change, this is in line with Innovative Work Behavior which is expected to be able to maximize the level of innovation maturity in the Cooperative Services in West Sumatra and can have the opportunity to receive the Innovative Government Award from the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia as an appreciation for implementing innovations to improve the implementation of regional government.

In line with this, according to the opinion M. Li et al., (2017) which states that Innovative Work Behavior has been proven to be a major factor contributing to organizational success. In addition, according to Sarwoko (2020) also stated that the competitive advantage of an organization is determined by the innovative behavior of employees. This is in accordance with the Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986) which states that an organization cannot be effective in achieving its goals without being supported by individual and team level work results. According to Dhir & Shukla (2019) the main component of organizational performance is individual work and refers to the formation of groups of employees who work together towards common goals. Good organizational management can be implemented if the organization's priorities have been implemented properly according to plan (Yuspahrudin et al., 2020). This shows that organizational performance is determined by the Innovative Work Behavior of individuals in the organization, which is shown by the ability to produce, promote, and realize new ideas in the organization.

Based on the results of an initial survey of employees of the Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region in October 2024, information was obtained that some employees working in the Regency/City Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region tend to still not have optimal Innovative Work Behavior, especially in terms of idea generation. Afsar et al., (2020); Sarwoko (2020) And Uppathampracha & Liu (2022) states that innovative work behavior can be seen from the employee's ability to generate ideas. At work the employees of the West Sumatra Cooperative Service are still fixated on existing fixed procedures so that they rarely look for new technical methods or work instruments so that employees are still less able to make work more effective and efficient in utilizing time, and it is also indicated that they are still less than optimal in producing solutions to a problem even though in working, leaders provide opportunities for their employees to create new approaches through

creating ideas for effectiveness in working. The creation of ideas that are still minimally utilized by employees, because employees tend to follow existing procedures in working because they feel that these procedures are the most appropriate and comfortable to work on.

According to Bandura (1986) behavior humans are caused by personal, behavioral, and environmental influences. Social Cognitive Theory argues that part of an individual's knowledge acquisition can be directly related to observing others in the context of social interactions, experiences, and external media influences. The theory states that when people observe models performing a behavior and the consequences of that behavior, they remember the sequence of events and use this information to guide subsequent behavior (Firmansyah & Saepuloh, 2022). This shows that the behavioral actions carried out by a person are able to demonstrate Innovative Work Behavior.

One of the factors that influence Innovative Work Behavior is Proactive Personality. Being proactive is associated with constructive work results, the reason is that Proactive Personality shows proactive behavior (C. Li et al., 2020). Individual the proactive are willing to act to change their circumstances intentionally (Bakker et al., 2012). Individuals with Proactive Personality tend to actively improve the existing environment or create new environments and take the initiative to challenge the status quo rather than passively adapting and then exhibiting active change behavior (Pan et al., 2021). This shows that individuals have a Proactive Personality not only sitting still waiting for tasks given by the agency but he tends to be more active in looking for and doing a job.

In addition to influencing Innovative Work Behavior, Proactive Personality also influences work engagement. Proactive personality fit can affect followers' engagement with work. Proactive Personality refers to an individual's enduring behavioral tendency to take the initiative to improve a current situation. Followers with high Proactive Personality are more engaged in work (K. Yang et al., 2017). Proactive Personality is positively related to engagement because individuals who are (proactively) engaged in their work environment also tend to immerse themselves in their work (Chong et al., 2021). Proactive Personality makes employees tend to take initiative and look for opportunities, and employees with high Proactive Personality tend to be diligent in carrying out their work tasks until they achieve their goals (Bakker et al., 2012).

Based on the results of an initial survey of employees of the Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region in October 2024, information was obtained that some employees working in the Regency/City Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region still tend not to have a maximum Proactive Personality, especially in terms of excel in identifying opportunities. This is caused by one of the reasons being the limited level of final education which is dominated by Bachelor's (S1) / D4, so that the shift in job class or promotion of the State Civil Apparatus is limited, because for these employees the opportunities indicated are there for affect a person's work environment is by shifting job classes or job promotions.

The next factor that influences Innovative Work Behavior is Entrepreneurial Leadership. Entrepreneurial Leadership has been highlighted as influencing corporate innovation through creating and communicating an inspiring entrepreneurial vision for the business, acting as a role model for innovative behavior and guiding employees through the process of generating and implementing new ideas. To encourage innovation in their companies, entrepreneurial leaders also create strategic procedures to maximize innovation and allocate appropriate resources and support for innovation and opportunity recognition (Bagheri et al., 2022).

According to entrepreneurial leadership theory, entrepreneurial leadership is a type of leadership that is effective for building teams to achieve goals Objective innovation (Renko et al., 2015). The term Entrepreneurial

Leadership refers to one of the leadership characteristics that leads to innovation (Renko et al., 2015). Entrepreneurial Leadership is a leadership style related to entrepreneurial traits. In the Trait Theories approach, a person can become a leader if he has the traits needed by a leader. This theory states that the success of a leader is determined by personality traits both physically and psychologically. The effectiveness of a leader is determined by the nature, temperament or personality traits that not only come from talent, but from experience and learning outcomes. This approach emphasizes the traits of a leader such as personality, motivation, values, and skills. The basis of this approach is the assumption that some people have leadership talents that have certain traits that are not possessed by others (Mu'ah et al., 2019).

Besides influencing Innovative Work Behavior, Entrepreneurial Leadership also influences work engagement. Papalexandris & Galanaki (2009) found that entrepreneurial leadership has a strong influence on employee engagement. Employee engagement can be formed through the leader's ability to motivate and direct, as well as convince his employees of achieving organizational goals. Leaders not only act as superiors, but must also be able to be good mentors for their employees. Employees who are amazed by the actions taken by leaders can increase employee engagement.

Based on the results of an initial survey of employees of the Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region in October 2024, information was obtained that some employees working in the Regency/City Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region still tend not to have optimal Entrepreneurial Leadership, especially in terms of often come up with truly new service ideas that the organization can provide and have creative solutions to problems at work. The reason is that when viewed from the main tasks and job functions carried out by employees, employees assume that if they come up with ideas and provide creative solutions, then the employee is the one who must implement the ideas and creative solutions that are conveyed to solve problems so that it complicates the employee's work and makes employees prefer not to convey and be neutral and work according to the main tasks and functions assigned. In addition, there are employees who assume that some of the main tasks and job functions of employees cannot apply creative solutions to overcome problems if they occur. This can certainly result in the superior program which is a derivative of the vision and mission of the Province of West Sumatra to produce 100 thousand millennial entrepreneurs and women entrepreneurs as well as creative economic actors being indicated as difficult to be realized optimally.

The last factor that influences Innovative Work Behavior is work engagement. Work engagement has been recognized by academics and practitioners as a factor that must be studied because it can encourage employees to take actions that lead to Innovative Work Behavior (Lauring & Selmer, 2015; Selmer & Lauring, 2015). Employees who demonstrate engagement with their work are more likely to demonstrate Innovative Work Behavior by suggesting and implementing ideas that can bring improvements in existing processes and create new and untapped opportunities (Afsar et al., 2020; Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022) Based on the results of an initial survey of employees of the Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region in October 2024, obtained information that some employees working in the Regency/City Cooperative Service in the West Sumatra region still tend to not have maximum work engagement, especially in terms of vigor. Work engagement is characterized by vigor. (Bakker et al., 2012; Agarwal, 2014a; K. Yang et al., 2017; Lv et al., 2018; Afsar et al., 2020). In this context vigor is defined as having high levels of energy and mental resilience, namely the willingness to invest effort in one's work and persist at work-related tasks (Afsar et al., 2020). When viewed from the main tasks and job functions carried out by employees at the West Sumatra Cooperative Service, employees who consistently work in the office are indicated to be less enthusiastic in working because a constant work

environment will cause a level of boredom and decreased enthusiasm, in contrast to those who experience changes in the work environment by going to the field to provide public services to the community will have high work enthusiasm because they get a changing work environment so they do not experience boredom.

Work engagement also mediates the influence proactive personality and entrepreneurial leadership towards Innovative Work Behavior. Several studies confirm that work engagement contains levels of motivation and enthusiasm, with commitment to work tasks (Buil et al., 2019). Increased engagement provides proactive behavior in the workplace in the form of personal initiative. Buil et al., (2019) states that individuals with Proactive Personality are actively involved in assigned tasks and citizenship behavior. Previous research states that Proactive Personality tends to be more enthusiastic in working, complex work tasks, and handle resources in a more effective way with new ideas to build work engagement (Bai et al., 2022). Behavioral engagement is one of the characteristics of work engagement, which is considered the most important trait to have to achieve success in business, which increases Innovative Work Behavior among employees (Wang et al., 2017). Then the entrepreneurial leader takes risks, influences, and guides employee performance (Renko et al., 2015) and encourage them to understand the needs of the organization by working creatively and innovatively (Fontana & Musa, 2017).

Research that examines the relationship between variables proactive personality, entrepreneurial leadership, work engagement and innovative work behavior, has been done a lot. Among them Iqbal et al., (2022) research on Entrepreneurial Leadership and employee innovative behavior: an examination through various theoretical lenses. Pan et al., (2021) research on the relationship between preschool teachers' Proactive Personality and innovative behavior: the mediating role of error management chain and self-efficacy.

M. Li et al., (2017) research on Proactive Personality and Innovative Work Behavior: the mediating effect of affective state and creative self-efficacy on teachers. Bagheri et al., (2022) research on how Entrepreneurial Leadership influences innovation work behavior? The mediating role of individual and team creativity self-efficacy. Akbari et al., (2021) research on whether Entrepreneurial Leadership encourages innovative work behavior? The mediating role of creativity and self-efficacy and support for innovation. Sarwoko (2020) research on entrepreneurial leadership and Innovative Work Behavior: the role of creative self-efficacy. Bai et al., (2022) researching the impact of authentic leadership on Innovative Work Behavior: the mediating role of Proactive Personality and employee engagement. Uppathampracha & Liu (2022) research on leading for innovation: self-efficacy and work engagement as sequential mediators linking ethical leadership and Innovative Work Behavior. Lv et al., (2018) research on team autonomy strengthens the positive effect of Proactive Personality on work engagement.

Based on in the previous research presented above, there are several research gaps, namely, first, not all research uses mediating variables. Work engagement to influence Innovative Work Behavior. Second, the objects and subjects of previous research are diverse so that they are considered not yet generalizable to the Cooperatives Service in West Sumatra, which has different characteristics and objectives. Innovative Work Behavior employees are also different. Third, there are research results that have an influence and do not have an influence between research variables. Fourth, the study of the influence between variables that is carried out is still dominant in companies or private organizations or institutions, in this case private companies (corporations), only a very small number of studies on the relationship between these variables have been carried out on public organizations or institutions, in this case government agencies, such as those carried out by M. Li et al., (2017) research on Proactive Personality and Innovative Work Behavior: the mediating effect of affective state and

creative self-efficacy on teachers. Fifth, there has been no previous research that combines Proactive Personality and Entrepreneurial Leadership as a variable that influences Innovative Work Behavior, and use work engagement as a mediating variable. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a more in-depth analysis related to the Innovative Work Behavior of Civil Servants of the Cooperative Service in West Sumatra.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Cognitive Theory

Social Cognitive Theory based on the proposition that social processes and cognitive processes are central to understanding about motivation, emotion, and human action. This theoretical perspective views human behavior as a component of a model that interacts with each other and influences the components of the environmental situation, as well as the personal components of humans which include individual affection/emotion and cognition (Abdullah, 2019).

According to Bandura (1986) human behavior is caused by personal, behavioral, and environmental influences. Social Cognitive Theory argues that part of an individual's knowledge acquisition can be directly related to observing others in the context of social interactions, experiences, and external media influences. The theory states that when people observe models performing behavior and the consequences of that behavior, they remember the sequence of events and use this information to guide subsequent behavior (Firmansyah & Saepuloh, 2022).

Bandura (1986), stated that Social Cognitive Theory is a learning theory based on the idea that people learn by observing others. This learned behavior can become the core of a person's personality. While social psychologists agree that the environment in which a person grows up contributes to an individual's behavior so that cognition is equally important. People learn by observing others, with the environment, behavior, and cognition all being major factors in influencing development in a reciprocal triadic relationship (Firmansyah & Saepuloh, 2022).

Bandura (1986) in the social cognitive model, the causal model involves triadic reciprocal determinism. In this model, the reciprocal causality of behavior, cognition and other personal factors, and environmental influences all operate as determinants that interact to influence each other. In more detail, Bandura explains that triadic reciprocal determinism is a model consisting of three factors that influence behavior, namely environment, individual, and behavior itself. Basically, Bandura believes that individual behavior is influenced by environmental factors and personal characteristics. The environmental component consists of the physical environment around the individual that has the potential to reinforce stimuli, including the social environment, namely the people who are present (or not). The environment affects the intensity and frequency of behavior, just as the behavior itself can have an impact on the environment. The individual component includes all of the characteristics of the self that have been built up from the past to the present. Personality and cognitive factors play an important role in causing how a person behaves, including all of the individual's expectations, beliefs, and unique personality characteristics. The behavioral component is a behavior that can be reinforced at any time or in certain situations (Abdullah, 2019).

Entrepreneurial Leadership Theory

According to entrepreneurial leadership theory, entrepreneurial leadership is a type of leadership that is effective in building teams to achieve innovation goals (Renko et al., 2015). The term Entrepreneurial Leadership refers to one of the leadership characteristics that leads to innovation. Entrepreneurial Leadership is

defined as a type of leadership that focuses on recognizing and exploiting opportunities to build teams to achieve innovation goals (Renko et al., 2015).

Entrepreneurial leadership can be shown by a leader through the entrepreneurial skills he has. Entrepreneurial Leadership refers to a leader who is able to take risks, seize opportunities, pursue innovation and be innovative, productive, exchange and strategic. A leader who has an entrepreneurial spirit has the ability to recognize himself and his environment very well. He also has the advantage of finding new opportunities (Mu'ah et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurial leadership is a leadership style related to entrepreneurial traits. Entrepreneurial Leadership is not only limited to the business world, but can also be applied in various fields, including government. This leadership style can have a big positive impact in creating sustainable change and growth. One of the focuses of Entrepreneurial Leadership theory is on the leadership traits possessed by individuals. This can be seen from researchers trying to identify entrepreneurial traits that distinguish successful leaders from unsuccessful ones.

In the Trait Theories approach, a person can become a leader if he has the traits needed by a leader. This theory states that the success of a leader is determined by personality traits both physically and psychologically. The effectiveness of a leader is determined by the nature, temperament or personality traits that not only come from talent, but from experience and learning outcomes. This approach emphasizes the traits of a leader such as personality, motivation, values, and skills. The basis of this approach is the assumption that some people have leadership talents that have certain traits that are not possessed by others (Mu'ah et al., 2019).

Innovative Work Behavior

Understanding Innovative Work Behavior is needed to develop innovation. Innovative behavior is involvement in the innovation process as an early part of innovative results (Sarwoko, 2020). Innovative behavior is a cognitive and motivational process directed at introducing, developing, and implementing new ideas to provide useful and novel solutions to problems (Iqbal et al., 2022). This shows that the concept of innovative behavior is broader than creativity because innovative behavior includes various activities ranging from championing ideas to implementing new processes, while the focus of creativity is narrower only on generating new ideas that are useful. Creativity includes exploring and generating ideas, while innovation includes championing and implementing ideas. Innovative Work Behavior connects employee work activities and results, which influences the development of innovation (Sarwoko, 2020).

Innovative work behavior refers to a complex set of actions intended to generate, promote, and realize new ideas within an organization, and has been shown to be a major factor contributing to organizational success (M. Li et al., 2017). A similar thing was stated by Bai et al., (2022) that Innovative Work Behavior is defined as employee efforts to offer new ideas, innovation and also support innovation to achieve organizational goals..

Besides that Innovative Work Behavior is also defined as the deliberate creation, introduction, and application of new ideas within a group or organizational work role, to benefit group or organizational performance (Kim & Park, 2017). This is in line with the opinion expressed by Uppathampracha & Liu (2022) that Innovative Work Behavior is defined as individual behavior that aims to initiate and intentionally introduce new and valuable ideas, processes, products, or procedures in a work role, group, or organization. In relation to this, Innovative Work Behavior can also be defined as individual behavior to achieve the initiation and intentional introduction (in a work role, group or organization) of new and useful ideas, processes, products or procedures (Hsiao et al., 2011). Individual Innovative Work Behavior activities in organization includes seeking out

advanced ideas, advocating for ideas in the workplace, and raising funds or arranging to execute the idea (Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022).

Work Engagement

Job engagement is a discretionary effort achieved through behavioral investment of physical, cognitive, and emotional energy into the work role. It involves the investment of “hands, head, and heart” in active and full work performance (Agarwal, 2014a). Work engagement is an affective-motivational condition of work-related well-being that is permanent and widespread and does not depend on specific objects, situations or people (Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022). This shows work engagement is an illusory force that motivates employees to improve their performance at a higher level, this energy is in the form of commitment to the organization, a sense of belonging to the job and pride, more effort (time and energy), enthusiasm and interest, and also commitment in carrying out the work.

Besides that work engagement is associated with positive mental attitudes at work that lead to positive work-related outcomes (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). This shows work engagement is a condition where a person has positive thoughts so that he is able to express himself physically, cognitively and affectively in doing his work. Wang et al., (2017) state A person's work engagement is indicated by vigor, dedication, and absorption which indicate high work enthusiasm, concentration, and involvement, thus inherently prohibiting counterproductive work behavior.

An organization can build a work environment that can make employees have work engagement by providing job resources, social support, and training. Employee work engagement is influenced by management if they provide adequate resources because it helps them get new services and properties. Work engagement is considered important for the success of the organization because they tend to be more committed important resources (Bai et al., 2022).

Proactive Personality

Proactive personality refers to the tendency to take personal initiative to actively identify opportunities and influence one's work environment (Lv et al., 2018). Proactive individuals are willing to act to change their circumstances intentionally (Bakker et al., 2012) by persisting until meaningful change occurs (Lv et al., 2018). Proactive Personality is a unique dispositional characteristic defined as a behavioral tendency to take personal initiative in creating a favorable environment (Wang et al., 2017).

Furthermore, another opinion that complements this is: Bai et al., (2022) which states that Proactive Personality defined as a relatively stable tendency to form changes that occur in environmental variations. Then, according to Chong et al., (2021) Proactive Personality is defined as a person's relatively stable tendency to take the initiative to bring about changes in themselves and/or their environment, thereby encouraging enthusiastic involvement with work and persistence in pursuing goals. This shows Proactive Personality is an initiative taken from within an individual to contribute to changes in the environment that can have an impact on the individual himself or on the environment through identifying opportunities. Proactive Personality reflects an interactive structure that states that individual behavior is in a dimension that can change events and the environment. Because of its structure, Proactive Personality leads individuals to see opportunities for growth. Proactive Personality involves creating new possibilities for the existing order to be more favorable and challenging rather than passively complying with the usual conditions (Doğanülkü & Korkmaz, 2023).

Proactive Personality can be defined as a personality trait that is relatively unconstrained by situational forces and has the ability to influence environmental change. Individuals with Proactive Personality tend to have traits that are not limited by certain situations and have the ability to influence change in their environment. They not only respond to the environment, but also try to take the initiative in creating the desired change (Afero et al., 2023). Proactive employees are valuable to organizations. They are characterized as people who are not constrained by situational limitations and tend to seek opportunities to shape one's environment by bringing about meaningful change. Proactive employees' tendency to shape the environment provides a number of advantages such as being more likely to negotiate job procedures and content, exert influence to expand available job resources, change or seek better ways to complete job tasks, and engage in career management activities (Wang et al., 2017). Employees who have Proactive Personality are able to handle situations according to needs. They predict scenarios and react accordingly because they think first in exploring the environment or work environment (Bai et al., 2022). Employees who have a Proactive Personality are very interested in new things and practices that enable them to think of innovative ideas for improvement and better results (Bergeron et al., 2014). Proactive employees tend to take the initiative to contribute above and beyond role requirements (Wang et al., 2017).

Entrepreneurial Leadership

Entrepreneurial Leadership defined as the ability of a leader to generate a compelling vision for the business and inspire and direct employees to strive and realize that vision. Entrepreneurial Leadership is a unique leadership style that is needed to overcome challenges and difficulties in various stages of organizational development. This leadership style empowers leaders to coordinate their organizations effectively and solve problems through various stages of challenging organizational development and improvement (Akbari et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurial Leadership is a specific leadership style that directs and facilitates followers to achieve superior performance and meet organizational goals by recognizing and exploiting entrepreneurial opportunities through their creative contributions (Renko et al., 2015). This is in line with the opinion put forward that Entrepreneurial Leadership is leadership behavior that encourages followers to identify and utilize entrepreneurial opportunities for the creation of mark (Iqbal et al., 2022) and thus aims to motivate employees to engage in creative activities (W. Cai et al., 2019)

Entrepreneurial Leadership focuses on recognizing and exploiting opportunities as an entrepreneurial goal (Renko et al., 2015). In addition, Entrepreneurial Leadership focuses on innovation and adaptation to environmental changes (Sarwoko, 2020).including exploiting new opportunities and increasing competitive capabilities (Huang et al., 2014). According to entrepreneurial leadership theory, Entrepreneurial Leadership is an effective type of leadership for building teams to achieve innovation goals (Renko et al., 2015). The term Entrepreneurial Leadership refers to one of the leadership characteristics that leads to innovation. Entrepreneurial Leadership is defined as a type of leadership that focuses on recognizing and exploiting opportunities to build teams to achieve innovation goals (Renko et al., 2015).

Entrepreneurial Leadership is considered as effective leadership in facing a dynamic business environment because it can increase innovation and recognize opportunities (Fontana & Musa, 2017). Entrepreneurial Leadership adopts a philosophy and management method that allows the integration of knowledge for use in new operations, processes and products (Gupta & Batra, 2016). It is important to encourage the development of Entrepreneurial Leadership at all levels of the organization to ensure that the innovation process is managed

effectively (Fontana & Musa, 2017). This is because the competitive advantage of an organization is determined by the innovative behavior of employees (Sarwoko, 2020). The role of Entrepreneurial Leadership is to develop strategies and approaches, facilitate innovation, support new ideas by employees (Bagheri, 2017), and recognizing opportunities perceived by employees (Huang et al., 2014).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used in this study is explanatory research. Explanatory research is a type of research used to explain the position between the variables studied and also explain the relationship between the variables. One with others through testing the formulated hypothesis. Meanwhile, the research approach uses an explanatory survey that emphasizes quantitative research methods (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The population used is the entire population Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra totaling 664 people, with a sample size of 250 people. The sampling technique used was proportionate stratified random sampling (Sugiyono, 2021). The types and sources of data used in this study are primary data. Data collection techniques use questionnaire techniques. The distribution of questionnaires in this study used a google form that was distributed directly to respondents and also used a questionnaire that was given directly to respondents. The questionnaire design was measured using a Likert scale (Sugiyono, 2021). Data analysis in this study used Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) (Hair et al., 2014). Mediation testing strategy using theory Hair et al., (2017) using the significance of the path coefficient. Furthermore, the measurements for each research variable can be explained as follows:

Table 2 Measurement of Research Variables

Variables	Indicator	Statement items	Source of indicators
Innovative Work Idea Exploration Behavior	Thinking about improvement.	Pay attention to issues that are not part of the job.	(Afsar et al., 2020)
		Looking for new work methods, techniques or instruments.	(Sarwoko, 2020)
	Idea generation	Generating original solutions.	Hartog,
		Finding a new approach.	
Idea championing	Idea championing	Encourage enthusiasm for innovative ideas.	
		Convincing to support innovative ideas.	
	Idea implementation	Introducing innovative ideas. Contribute to the implementation of new ideas. . Developing new things	
Proactive Personality		Looking for new ways.	(F. Yang & Chau, 2016)
		Be a force for constructive change.	(K. Yang et al., 2017)
		Love the idea of turning it into reality.	(M. Li et al., 2017)
		Fix something you don't like.	(Lv et al., 2018)
		Be confident and persistent.	(Pan et al., 2021)
		Fighting for ideas.	(Doğanülkü & Korkmaz,
		Excels in identifying opportunities.	
Looking for a better way.			

2023)
(Seibert et al., 1999)

Never give up.

0. Finding a good opportunity.

Entrepreneurial Coming up with radical improvement ideas. (Sarwoko, 2020)

Leadership Generating new service ideas. (Iqbal et al., 2022)

Dare to take risks. (Bagheri et al., 2022)

Have creative solutions. (Renko et al., 2015)

Demonstrate work ethic.

Have a vision of the future of the organization.

Act more innovatively.

Challenging the way organizations deliver services.

Work Vigor High work spirit. (Bakker et al., 2012) engagement Strong and

passionate. (Agarwal, 2014a)

Feeling like going to work. (K. Yang et al., 2017)

Dedication Enthusiastic about work. (Bai et al., 2022) Inspiring work. (Schaufeli et al., 2006)

Proud of work.

Absorption Work seriously.

Lost in work.

Get carried away by the atmosphere while working.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Measurement model defines how each indicator block relates to its latent variables. This model is used to determine the construct validity and construct reliability. This model is evaluated using convergent and discriminant validity of its indicators and composite reliability and Cronbach's Alpha for the indicator blocks.(Hair et al., 2014).

Convergent Validity and Construct Reliability Test

Convergent validity the value is obtained by looking at the correlation between the item score and the construct score. The provision for stating that an individual indicator is valid is when it has a correlation value (outer loading) > 0.70 and AVE > 0.50. Furthermore, if the AVE value is > 0.50, then the outer loading can use a value > 0.50 (Hair et al., 2014). Measurement of construct reliability uses two assessments in the form of composite reliability and cronbach alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. Furthermore, to state a reliable construct can be seen from the composite reliability value or cronbach alpha which is above 0.70 (Hair et al., 2014). The following are the results of the convergent validity test seen based on the outer loading and AVE values as well as the test results and construct reliability in table 3:

Table 3 Convergent AVE Values and Variables			Validity Test Results Based on Outer Loading and Construct Reliability		
Item	Outer Loading	AVE	Item	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Entrepreneurial Leadership	0.652	0.923	KK2	0.853	0.859
	0.923	0.937	KK3	0.828	
	0.937		KK4	0.844	
			KK5	0.774	
			KK6	0.778	
			KK7	0.757	
			KK8	0.758	
			KP10	0.719	0.710
			KP2	0.733	
			KP3	0.814	
			KP4	0.746	
			KP5	0.796	
			KP6	0.801	

Proactive Personality	0.569	0.915	0.929
KP7	0.761	KTK2	0.795
		KTK3	0.838
		KTK4	0.834
		KTK5	0.768
		KTK6	0.830
		KTK7	0.718
		KTK8	0.806

		KP8	0.735
		KP9	0.709

Work engagement	0.620	0.923	0.936
KTK9	0.764	KTK1	0.725

Innovative Behavior	0.710	Work	PK11
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0.628	0.934	0.944	PKI10	0.779
PKI9	0.809		PKI2	0.732
			PKI3	0.834
			PKI4	0.856
			PKI5	0.822
			PKI6	0.827
			PKI7	0.764
			PKI8	0.777

Source: Results of primary data processing (2024)

In this study, the outer loading value used was 0.70 referring to the theory put forward Hair et al., (2014) that individual indicators are declared valid when they have a correlation value (outer loading) above or greater than 0.70 and AVE > 0.50. Based on table 3, it can be seen that if referring to the required outer loading value of 0.70, it can be explained that all statement items in the variables used in the form of Proactive Personality, Entrepreneurial Leadership, work engagement and Innovative Work Behavior have met the requirements, where the value of each outer loading for each statement item is > 0.70, so that all statement items are declared valid. Then the AVE value was also found for all variables used > 0.50, which means that the statement is valid according to the convergent validity criteria so that it can be continued to the next stage, namely the discriminant validity test. From Table 3 above, it shows that the Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability values for all variables are greater than 0.70, which indicates that all variables are declared reliable

Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity the assessment uses cross loading construct. The provisions are as follows, if the correlation of the construct with the measurement item is greater than the size of other constructs, then this indicates that the latent construct predicts the size of their block better than the size of other blocks (Hair et al., 2014). The following are the results of the discriminant validity test seen based on the cross loading value:

Table 4 Results of Discriminant Validity Testing Based on Cross Loading Values

	Entrepreneurial Leadership	Proactive Personality	Work engagement	Innovative Work Behavior
KK1	0.859	0.596	0.577	0.626
KK2	0.853		0.643	0.588
KK3	0.828		0.588	0.541
KK4	0.844		0.596	0.608
KK5	0.774		0.635	0.752
KK6	0.778		0.591	0.611
KK7	0.757		0.601	0.556
KK8	0.758		0.599	0.570
KP1	0.532		0.719	0.457
KP10	0.623		0.719	0.533
KP2	0.558		0.733	0.432
KP3	0.486		0.814	0.489
KP4	0.621	0.746	0.569	0.571

KP5	0.566	0.796	0.500	0.557
KP6	0.471	0.801	0.472	0.532
KP7	0.559	0.761	0.504	0.589
KP8	0.637	0.735	0.567	0.551
KP9	0.597	0.709	0.500	0.490
KTK1	0.591	0.476	0.725	0.482
KTK2	0.668	0.558	0.795	0.560
KTK3	0.540	0.508	0.838	0.496
KTK4	0.626	0.474	0.834	0.506
KTK5	0.570	0.561	0.768	0.654
KTK6	0.609	0.580	0.830	0.538
KTK7	0.601	0.576	0.718	0.509
KTK8	0.552	0.507	0.806	0.509
KTK9	0.532	0.479	0.764	0.478
PKI1	0.681	0.599	0.573	0.710
PKI10	0.558	0.500	0.490	0.779
PKI2	0.672	0.579	0.618	0.732
PKI3	0.596	0.628	0.497	0.834
PKI4	0.577	0.629	0.509	0.856
PKI5	0.597	0.634	0.520	0.822
PKI6	0.582	0.615	0.552	0.827
PKI7	0.587	0.580	0.509	0.764
PKI8	0.645	0.604	0.542	0.777
PKI9	0.557	0.540	0.482	0.809

Source: Results of primary data processing (2024)

In table 4, it can be seen that the correlation value of the variables Proactive Personality, Entrepreneurial Leadership, work engagement and Innovative Work Behavior to their indicators is greater than the correlation value of the indicators to other variables, this shows that all indicator values tested in this study are declared valid, so it can be concluded that all variable indicators in this study have good discriminant validity.

Structural Model Testing (Inner model)

The structural assessment model uses R-square as well as t-test and significance of parameter coefficients to test the hypothesis.

R-Square Assessment

The R-square value is used to assess the ability of exogenous latent variables to explain endogenous latent variables whether they have substantive explanatory ability. Where if the R-Square value is 0.75 indicates a strong model, 0.50 a medium model and

0.25 a weak model (Hair et al., 2014). The estimated R-square value can be seen in Table 5 below.

Table 5 R-Square Assessment

R-Square
0.587

Work engagement

Innovative Work Behavior 0.666

Source: Results of primary data processing (2024)

From table 5 it can be seen that the R-Square value for the work engagement variable is 0.587. This value shows that 58.7% of employee work engagement variables can be explained by Proactive Personality and Entrepreneurial Leadership, while the remaining 41.3% is explained by other variables not explained in this study, where the model's explanatory ability is moderate because $0.587 > 0.50$ but smaller than 0.75.

The R-Square value for the Innovative Work Behavior variable is 0.666. This value shows that 66.6% of Innovative Work Behavior can be explained by Proactive Personality, Entrepreneurial Leadership and work engagement, while the remaining 33.4% is explained by other variables not explained in this study, where the model's explanatory ability is moderate because $0.666 > 0.50$ but smaller than 0.75.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis test/significance value can be obtained from the output results of the path coefficient (Mean, std-*dv*, and Tvalue). Furthermore, the original sample value is used to indicate a positive (+) or negative (-) correlation. A hypothesis is accepted if the calculated t value $>$ t table with a confidence level of 95% or a significance level of 5%, where if the calculated t has a significance of less than 0.05, it means that it has a significant influence. In this study, the hypothesis test results were declared accepted for the one-tailed hypothesis results (1-way hypothesis) with the provision of a t-statistic value greater than the t table value (1.65) for a significance level of 0.05 (Hair et al., 2014). The results of the bootstrapping test to obtain significance values for the hypothesis test in this study can be seen in the following table:

Table 6 Path Coefficient Results and Indirect Effect Results

				Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
H1	Proactive Personality -> Work engagement			0.242	0.239	0.068	3,552	0,000
H2	Proactive Personality -> Innovative Work Behavior			0.364	0.370	0.061	5,967	0,000
H3	Work engagement -> Innovative Work Behavior			0.132	0.130	0.061	2,185	0.015
H4	Entrepreneurial Leadership -> Work engagement			0.567	0.571	0.059	9,557	0,000
H5	Entrepreneurial Leadership -> Innovative Work Behavior			0.396	0.395	0.081	4,890	0,000
H6	Proactive Personality -> Work			0.032	0.031	0.018	1,745	0.041

	engagement -> Innovative Work Behavior					
H7	Entrepreneurial Leadership -> Work engagement -> Innovative Work Behavior	0.075	0.074	0.035	2.121	0.017

Source: Primary data processing results (2024)

The effect of Proactive Personality on Work engagement

The results of the first hypothesis test show that the original sample value of the effect of Proactive Personality on work engagement is positive at 0.242, indicating that the direction of the effect is positive. The t-statistics value is $3.552 > 1.65$ with a pvalue of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that Proactive Personality has a positive and significant effect on work engagement, thus the first hypothesis is accepted. This shows that it is getting better Proactive Personality of employees then it will increase further employee work engagement.

When viewed from the Proactive Personality of the State Civil Apparatus of the Cooperative Service in West Sumatra generally more considerate always looking for new ways to improve the quality of his life to influence work engagement, where this has been proven - to be implemented very well, as can be seen from the highest assessment obtained at the respondent achievement level. Researchers found that most of the employees who were respondents in the study agree that they are always looking for new ways to improve their quality of life. This is because most of the employees' length of service is > 10 years, as many as 172 people (68.8%), where with these conditions, employees certainly consider their position which is influenced by culture, values, goals, expectations, standards, and concerns that they experience related to work, so considering new ways to improve the quality of life such as health, material comfort, personal security, relationships, and other things is important for them in order to influence their work engagement at the agency. In addition, the assessment of the Proactive Personality of the State Civil Apparatus of the Cooperative Service in West Sumatra which is considered to influence work engagement is in terms of if employees see something they don't like, they fix it and employees always look for better ways to do things, where both of these things have been proven to be implemented well, which can be seen from respondent achievement level. This is in accordance with the opinion expressed that proactive individuals are willing to act to change their circumstances intentionally (Bakker et al., 2012) by persisting until meaningful change occurs (Lv et al., 2018). Besides that Individuals who have a Proactive Personality are able to recharge their personal energy to handle situations first (Chong et al., 2021). Bandura (1986) stated in Social Cognitive Theory that there are three factors that influence behavior, namely environment, individual, and behavior itself. Personality and cognitive factors play an important role in causing how a person behaves (Abdullah, 2019). Proactive Personality refers to the tendency to take personal initiative to actively identify opportunities and influence one's work environment. Social Cognitive Theory states that the environment influences the intensity and frequency of behavior, just as the behavior itself can have an impact on the environment (Abdullah, 2019). A supportive environment and opportunities for innovation can encourage individuals to develop Proactive Personality. Where a positive and supportive work environment can increase work engagement. Work engagement is often triggered by intrinsic motivation, which can be influenced by cognitive factors such as personal goals and values. This suggests that individuals with Proactive Personality who have clear goals and feel that their work is meaningful tend to be more engaged or have higher levels of work engagement. These individuals are better able to overcome challenges and adapt to change, which increases their engagement with work. This shows that the fit of Proactive Personality can affect followers'

engagement with work. Proactive Personality refers to an individual's enduring behavioral tendency to take the initiative to improve the current situation. Followers with high Proactive Personality are more engaged in work (K. Yang et al., 2017). Active and engaged workers bring their energy to a job to gain enjoyment and activation. Being active is a basic component of energy in a similar way to work engagement. Individuals who have proactive behaviors can be more engaged in their work, because it recharges the energy that helps to be motivated and excited at work (Lv et al., 2018).

Chong et al., (2021) states that Proactive Personality is positively related to engagement because individuals who are (proactively) involved in their work environment also tend to immerse themselves in their work. Proactive Personality makes employees more likely to take initiative and seek opportunities, and employees with high Proactive Personality tend to persist in their work tasks until they achieve their goals (Bakker et al., 2012). Engaging in such behavior reflects a high level of absorption in work, indicating greater work engagement. On the other hand, employees who have low Proactive Personality tend to be passive recipients of environmental or social changes (Chong et al., 2021). Therefore, when employees have low Proactive Personality, they tend to do the minimal tasks required at work and tend not to be engrossed in their work, so that shows low work engagement (Chong et al., 2021).

Results Study this is consistent with several research findings that found Proactive Personality has a significant positive effect on work engagement (Bai et al., 2022). Proactive Personality has a significant positive effect on work engagement (Lv et al., 2018).

The effect of Proactive Personality on Innovative Work Behavior

Test results hypothesis second shows the original value of the sample of the influence of Proactive Personality on Innovative Work Behavior is positive at 0.364 which indicates that the direction of the effect is positive. The t-statistics value is $5.967 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that Proactive Personality has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior, thus the second hypothesis is accepted. This shows that the better the employee's Proactive Personality, the more the employee's Innovative Work Behavior will increase.

Proactive Personality is measured as a stimulus to adapt to changes and a person's ability to take action in advance according to environmental needs (Kumar & Shukla, 2019). Being proactive is associated with constructive work outcomes, the reason being that Proactive Personality exhibits proactive behavior (C. Li et al., 2020). Individuals with Proactive Personality tend to actively improve the existing environment or create new environments and take the initiative to challenge the status quo rather than passively adapting and then exhibiting active change behavior (Pan et al., 2021).

Proactive Personality has been proven to be implemented well in the Civil Service of the Cooperative Service in West Sumatra. Where this can be seen from the overall level of achievement of respondents Proactive Personality, so that all of these things affect the Innovative Work Behavior of employees as seen from in terms of idea exploration, idea generation, idea championing and idea implementation, all of these things were also carried out well Civil Service Apparatus of the Cooperatives Service in West Sumatra.

Bandura (1986) states that in Social Cognitive Theory there are Three factors that influence behavior are environment, individual, and behavior itself. Basically, Bandura believes that individual behavior is influenced by environmental factors and personal characteristics (Abdullah, 2019). A supportive and collaborative work environment can encourage individuals with Proactive Personality to engage in Innovative Work Behavior. In the context of Social Cognitive Theory, a positive environment can create experiences that reinforce innovative

behavior. For example, if employees feel safe to share ideas and experiment, they are more likely to innovate. When proactive individuals take initiative and innovate, and they receive positive feedback, they are more likely to continue engaging in Innovative Work Behavior. This positive reinforcement is consistent with the principles of Social Cognitive Theory, where positive experiences reinforce desired behavior. Proactive Personality is often driven by intrinsic motivation, which can be influenced by cognitive factors such as personal goals and values. Employees who have a clear sense of purpose and feel that their work is meaningful are more likely to engage in Innovative Work Behavior.

Based on the highest assessment of Proactive Personality as seen from the value respondent achievement rate (TCR), most employees 158 people (63.2%) who were respondents in the research agree that they are always looking for new ways to improve their quality of life so that it affects their Innovative Work Behavior. However, when viewed from Innovative Work Behavior, the idea generation indicator is the lowest level of respondent achievement even though it is carried out well. Where only some employees who were respondents in the study agreed that they were able to find new methods, techniques, or work instruments, produce original solutions to a problem, and find new approaches to carrying out tasks but still not optimal. This can happen because most employees do their main tasks and job functions with the same position from time to time so they don't pay much attention to new methods, techniques, or work instruments. In addition, employees feel that the solutions they provide are not all purely original in dealing with problems because sometimes the solutions have been used and also with the same main tasks and functions all the time they don't really care about finding new approaches to carrying out tasks.

Proactive Personality reflects an individual's tendency to act proactively. This trait refers to an individual's tendency to act proactively to bring about meaningful change in their environment. Proactive Personality is one of the important motivational sources of proactive behavior. Therefore, proactive people influence their environment through proactive behavior (Doğanülkü & Korkmaz, 2023)

Individuals who have an active approach are involved in risk taking and are inventive, resulting in Innovative Work Behavior. The performance and competitive success of the organization are aligned with Proactive Personality and Innovative Work Behavior (Yamak & Eyupoglu, 2021). In building an innovative work environment, Proactive Personality is an attribute that deserves attention, on the basis of being proactive in handling changes in the business atmosphere after analyzing complex situations or changes first. (Bai et al., 2022). Results study this is consistent with several research findings found that Proactive Personality has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior (M. Li et al., 2017; Bai et al., 2022).

The effect of Work engagement To Innovative Work Behavior

The results of the third hypothesis test show that the original sample value of the effect of work engagement on Innovative Work Behavior is positive at 0.132. Which shows that the direction of effect is positive. The t-statistic value is $2.185 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.015 < 0.05$. This shows that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior, thus the third hypothesis is accepted. This shows that the better the employee's work engagement, the more the employee's Innovative Work Behavior will increase.

If seen from work engagement The Civil Service of the Cooperatives Service in West Sumatra, based on the level of achievement of employee respondents, strongly agree that their work engagement in terms of vigor, dedication and absorption is carried out very well. so that all of these things influence employee Innovative Work Behavior.

Work engagement is an affective-motivational condition of work-related well-being that is permanent and widespread and does not depend on specific objects, situations or people (Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022). Work engagement has been recognized by academics and practitioners as a factor that must be studied because it can encourage employees to take action (Lauring & Selmer, 2015; Selmer & Lauring, 2015), which leads to Innovative Work Behavior. Positive employee behavior, including unrestricted and non-mandatory actions, as well as ingenuity, creativity, and innovation, are the result of work engagement (Afsar et al., 2020).

The highest assessment of the work engagement variable is in the dedication indicator which is seen from the respondent's achievement level value. Where most of the employees who were respondents in the study were very agree that their dedication is carried out very well. This can be seen from the responses of employees who generally agree that they are enthusiastic about their work, then their work inspires them and they are proud of the work they do. This can be seen from one of the majority of employees who dominate having a working period of > 10 years.

Work engagement motivates individuals to accept challenging situations without losing focus and dedication. Innovative Work Behavior is challenging because of the amount of effort required to actually implement innovative ideas, energy levels, mental resilience, focus, enjoyment, involvement, and internal drive to create impact that will help individuals engage in innovative efforts. Work engagement increases will employees to share their work-related knowledge with other members of the organization and/or actively suggest new ideas for their organization (Kim & Park, 2017), and transforming new ideas into successful applications, namely Innovative Work Behavior. Thus, employees who demonstrate engagement with their work are more likely to demonstrate Innovative Work Behavior by suggesting and implementing ideas that can bring improvements in existing processes and create new and untapped opportunities (Afsar et al., 2020; Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022). Bandura (1986) stated in Social Cognitive Theory that he basically believes that individual behavior is influenced by environmental factors and personal characteristics. Behavioral components are behaviors that can be strengthened at any time or in certain situations (Abdullah, 2019). In the context of Social Cognitive Theory, a supportive environment can create positive experiences that strengthen work engagement and have an impact on creating experiences that strengthen Innovative Work Behavior. Employees who are engaged in their work tend to have high levels of energy and high engagement deep with work. This energy can encourage them to think creatively and find new ways to complete tasks, which is the essence of innovative behavior. Where work engagement is often triggered by intrinsic motivation, which can increase employees' desire to innovate.

Employees who feel involved and excited about their work are more likely to find new solutions and contribute innovative ideas. When employees are engaged with their work and receive positive feedback, they are more likely to feel motivated to innovate. This positive reinforcement strengthens Innovative Work Behavior, because employees feel that their contributions are appreciated.

The relationship between work engagement and Innovative Work Behavior is recognized in previous research which explains that individuals with high levels of engagement tend to perform efficient work, engage in innovative ideas, And demonstrates new types of solutions to problems (Afsar et al., 2020) To get new ideas in the workplace, Innovative Work Behavior is the right function. Engaged employees tend to be more active with a higher level of energy and more passionate about work. Work engagement is closely related to Innovative Work Behavior. Thus, employee innovation and Innovative Work Behavior increase high levels of engagement and reduce short levels of engagement (Bai et al., 2022).

Results Study this is consistent with several research findings found that work engagement has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior (Agarwal, 2014a; Kim & Park, 2017; Afsar et al., 2020; Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022)

The effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Work Engagement

The results of the fourth hypothesis test show that the original sample value of the effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on work engagement is positive at 0.567, indicating that the direction of the effect is positive. The t-statistic value is $9.557 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that Entrepreneurial Leadership has a positive and significant effect on work engagement, thus the fourth hypothesis is accepted. This shows that the better the employee's Entrepreneurial Leadership, the more the employee's work engagement will increase.

If seen from Entrepreneurial Leadership, Civil Servants of the Cooperative Service in West Sumatra agree that their Entrepreneurial Leadership is well implemented in the Cooperative Service unit in West Sumatra. This is based on the overall level of achievement of respondents for Entrepreneurial Leadership, So all of these things affect employee work engagement.

The highest assessment for the Entrepreneurial Leadership variable based on the respondent's achievement level value is found in the statement item showing enthusiasm for the work being done which is carried out very well, where most of the...bigThe employees who were respondents in the study strongly agreed that they showed enthusiasm for the work they did. This can be seen from the employees doing their work in accordance with the main tasks and functions of the field they occupy, where each employee already has their own field of specialization so that they like and are enthusiastic about what they do.

Apart from that, the highest assessment is for employee Entrepreneurial Leadership based on the respondent's achievement level value considered to influence work engagement in the Civil Service of the Cooperative Service in West Sumatra is that employees have a vision of the future of the organization where they work, then the employee's work challenges and encourages employees to act in a more innovative way and the employee's work wants employees to challenge the way the organization currently provides services, all of which implemented well, so that all of these things also affect employee work engagement.

This is in accordance with the opinion expressed that Entrepreneurial Leadership can be demonstrated by a leader through the entrepreneurial skills he has. Leaders who have an entrepreneurial spirit have the ability to recognize themselves and their environment very well (Mu'ah et al., 2019). This shows that an individual in his/her work environment will demonstrate the form of Entrepreneurial Leadership that he/she has through a series of behaviors that support innovation, risk taking, and value creation that he/she does.

Bandura (1986) stated in Social Cognitive Theory that basically individual behavior is influenced by environmental factors and personal characteristics (Abdullah, 2019). Where this shows that in the context of Social Cognitive Theory Entrepreneurial Leadership, it can be used to understand how individuals who have an Entrepreneurial Leadership spirit shown through behavior can influence work engagement in an agency.

Papalexandris & Galanaki (2009) in his research looking for the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and employee engagement, he found that entrepreneurial leadership has a strong influence on employee engagement. Employee engagement can be formed through the leader's ability to motivate and direct, as well as convince his employee's of achievement of organizational goals. Leaders do not only act as superiors, but must also be able to be good mentors for their employees. Employees who are impressed by the actions taken by leaders can increase employee engagement. In addition, research conducted by Al Mehrzi & Singh (2016) explains that the role of a leader is crucial to employee engagement because the desire and motivation of

employees to reach out to the company is not only because of their love for the company or the work they do, but also because of the role of the leader. The characteristics of a leader such as protecting, supporting, and understanding their employees can also increase employee engagement (Agarwal et al., 2012).

Results study this is consistent with several research findings found that Entrepreneurial Leadership has a significant positive effect on work engagement (Pinela et al., 2022). Entrepreneurial Leadership has a significant positive effect on employee engagement (Yulivan, 2022).

The effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior

The results of the fifth hypothesis test show that the original sample value of the effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior is positive at 0.396, indicating that the direction of the effect is positive. The t-statistic value is 4.890>

1.65 With a p-value of 0.000 <0.05. This shows that Entrepreneurial Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior, thus the fifth hypothesis is accepted. This shows that the better the employee's Entrepreneurial Leadership, the more the employee's Innovative Work Behavior will increase.

When viewed from Innovative Work Behavior Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra, the highest assessment of Innovative Work Behavior as seen from the respondent's level of achievement is found in idea exploration indicator, where most of the employees who were respondents in the study agreed that they care about problems that are not part of their daily work by paying attention to them and being able to think about how to be responsible for their work so that they can improve their implementation properly. This is because when viewed from the length of service, employees are dominated by employees who have worked for > 10 years with an age dominated by > 48 years, where with these conditions employees have had long work experience and of course can pay attention to problems that are not part of the job, but at the same time also think about how their work can be improved over time.

This is in line with the assessment of Entrepreneurial Leadership, which is highest in terms of show enthusiasm for the work they do which is carried out very well. Where most of the employees who were respondents in the study strongly agreed that they showed enthusiasm for the work they did. This can be seen from the employees doing their work in accordance with the main tasks and functions of the field they occupy, where each employee already has their own field of specialization so that they like and are enthusiastic about what they do so that it affects employee Innovative Work Behavior.

Apart from that, the highest assessment is for employee Entrepreneurial Leadership based on the respondent's achievement level value which are considered to influence Innovative Work Behavior In the Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra, employees have a vision of the future of the organization where they work, then the employee's work challenges and encourages employees to act in a more innovative way and the employee's work requires employees to challenge the way the organization currently provides services, all of which implemented well, so that all of these things also influence employee Innovative Work Behavior.

Entrepreneurial Leadership has been highlighted as influencing corporate innovation through creating and communicating an inspiring entrepreneurial vision for the business, acting as a role model for innovative behavior and guiding employees through the process of generating and implementing new ideas (Bagheri et al., 2022). Entrepreneurial Leadership is a leadership style related to entrepreneurial traits. In the Trait Theory approach, a person can become a leader if he has the traits needed by a leader. This theory states that the success of a leader is determined by personality traits both physically and psychologically. The effectiveness of a leader is determined by the nature, temperament or personality traits that not only come from talent, but from

experience and learning outcomes. This approach emphasizes the traits of leaders such as personality, motivation, values, and skills. The basis of this approach is the assumption that some people have leadership talents that have certain traits that are not possessed by others (Mu'ah et al., 2019). Entrepreneurial leaders are not only involved in recognizing and exploiting opportunities but also emphasize the importance of such behavior. (Iqbal et al., 2022) and thereby act as role models and encourage followers to demonstrate innovation and creativity in their work activities (Miao et al., 2018; Newman, Neesham, et al., 2018)

Bandura (1986) stated in Social Cognitive Theory that behavioral components are behaviors that can be strengthened at any time or in certain situations (Abdullah, 2019). Individuals who have the spirit of Entrepreneurial Leadership have a series of distinctive behaviors that distinguish them from leaders in other contexts. Entrepreneurial Leadership can be demonstrated by a leader through the entrepreneurial skills he has. (Mu'ah et al., 2019). This shows that an employee who has Entrepreneurial Leadership behavior tends to support the environment through entrepreneurial skills that enable experimentation and innovation in the form of Innovative Work Behavior.

Results study this is consistent with several research findings found that Entrepreneurial Leadership has a significant positive influence on employee innovative behavior (Iqbal et al., 2022). Entrepreneurial Leadership has a significant positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior (Sarwoko, 2020). Entrepreneurial Leadership has a significant positive influence on employee innovation work behavior (Bagheri et al., 2022)

The effect of Proactive Personality towards Innovative Work Behavior Mediated Work engagement

The results of the sixth hypothesis test show that the original sample value of the effect of Proactive Personality on Innovative Work Behavior mediated by work engagement is positive at 0.032, indicating that the direction of the effect is positive. The t-statistics value is $1.745 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.041 < 0.05$. This shows that work engagement mediates the effect of Proactive Personality on Innovative Work Behavior, thus the sixth hypothesis is accepted.

Based on the results of the mediation effect test produced for the influence Proactive Personality towards Innovative Work Behavior with work engagement as mediation in the form of direct and indirect relationships, all of which are significant and have the same direction coefficient with a positive direction, so it can be concluded that the form of mediation is complementary mediation in the form of partial mediation referring to the theory Hair et al., (2017).

This indicates that work engagement as a mediating variable can be a mediator in the influence between Proactive Personality and Innovative Work Behavior at the Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra, due to work engagement seen from the perspective of vigor, dedication and absorption is things to consider Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra as an intermediary for the influence of Proactive Personality on employee Innovative Work Behavior.

For any organization, employees are a valuable resource and caring about their welfare is essential to building a healthy and conducive working environment (Yamak & Eyupoglu, 2021). Several studies confirm that work engagement involves a level of motivation and enthusiasm, with commitment to work tasks (Buil et al., 2019). Work engagement has attachment in various forms (e.g., trait attachment, behavioral attachment, and status attachment), to confirm that the characteristics of engagement are open to various theoretical and practical research (Lai et al., 2020)

Work engagement is a psychological state characterized by passion, dedication, and deep involvement in work. A positive and supportive work environment can increase work engagement. Bandura (1986) stated in Social

Cognitive Theory that there are three factors that influence behavior, namely environment, individual, and behavior itself. The environment affects the intensity and frequency of behavior, as the behavior itself can have an impact on the environment (Abdullah, 2019). In the context of Social Cognitive Theory, a supportive environment can create positive experiences that strengthen work engagement. When employees are engaged in their work and receive positive feedback, they are more likely to feel engaged. This positive reinforcement is consistent with the principles of Social Cognitive Theory, where positive experiences reinforce desired behaviors. Work engagement is often driven by intrinsic motivation, which can be influenced by cognitive factors such as personal goals and values. Social Cognitive Theory suggests that individuals who have a clear sense of purpose and feel that their work is meaningful tend to be more engaged.

Increased engagement provides proactive behavior in the workplace in the form of personal initiative. Buil et al., (2019) states that individuals with Proactive Personality are actively involved in the tasks given which is demonstrated through behavior. Proactive individuals will face challenges in representing their new initiatives and strive to see obstacles and see problems as opportunities (Young et al., 2018). Previous research states that Proactive Personality tends to be more enthusiastic in working, complex work tasks, and handling resources in a more effective way with new ideas to build work engagement (Bai et al., 2022). In addition, existing research finds that workplace performance and personal behaviors (i.e., Proactive Personality, self-efficacy) are the best predictors of employee work engagement because they encompass every aspect of employee effort to achieve goals.(D. Cai et al., 2018; Sengupta et al., 2020)

Behavioral engagement is one of the characteristics of work engagement, which is considered the most important trait to have to achieve success in business, which increases Innovative Work Behavior among employees (Wang et al., 2017). Innovation can provide an opportunity for every employee to offer their creative thinking to increase engagement with the work environment (Agarwal, 2014b).Results study this is consistent with the research results. Bai et al., (2022) who found that work engagement mediates the influence of proactive personality on Innovative Work Behavior.

The effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership towards Innovative Work Behavior Mediated Work engagement

The results of the seventh hypothesis test show that the original sample value of the effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior mediated by work engagement is positive at 0.075, indicating that the direction of the effect is positive. The t-statistics value is $2.121 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.017 < 0.05$. This shows that work engagement mediates the effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior, thus the seventh hypothesis is accepted. Based on the results of the mediation effect test produced for the influence Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior with work engagement as mediation in the form of direct and indirect relationships, all of which are significant and have the same direction coefficient with a positive direction, so it can be concluded that the form of mediation is complementary mediation in the form of partial mediation referring to the theory Hair et al., (2017).

This indicates that work engagement as a mediating variable can be a mediator of the influence between Entrepreneurial Leadership to Innovative Work Behavior at the Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra, due to work engagement seen from the perspective of vigor, dedication and absorption is things to consider Civil Service of the Cooperatives Department in West Sumatra as an intermediary for influence Entrepreneurial Leadership on employee Innovative Work Behavior.

Entrepreneurial Leadership can be demonstrated by a leader through his entrepreneurial skills. Leaders who have an entrepreneurial spirit have the ability to recognize themselves and their environment very well (Mu'ah et al., 2019). This shows that an individual in his/her work environment will demonstrate the form of Entrepreneurial Leadership that he/she has through a series of behaviors that support innovation, risk taking, and value creation that he/she does which will have an impact on work engagement in the agency. Then Employees who demonstrate engagement with their work are more likely to exhibit Innovative Work Behavior by suggesting and implementing ideas that can bring improvements in existing processes and create new and untapped opportunities (Afsar et al., 2020; Uppathampracha & Liu, 2022). This shows that work engagement can be used as a mediation (intermediary) between entrepreneurial leadership and Innovative Work Behavior.

Bandura (1986) stated in Social Cognitive Theory that there are three factors that influence behavior, namely environment, individual, and behavior itself. The environment influences the intensity and frequency of behavior, as behavior itself can have an impact on the environment (Abdullah, 2019). In the context of Social Cognitive Theory, a supportive environment can create positive experiences that strengthen work engagement. When employees are engaged in their work and receive positive feedback, they are more likely to feel engaged. This positive reinforcement is consistent with the principles of Social Cognitive Theory, where positive experiences reinforce desired behaviors. Work engagement is often fueled by intrinsic motivation, which can be influenced by cognitive factors such as personal goals and values. Social Cognitive Theory suggests that individuals who have a clear sense of purpose and feel that their work is meaningful tend to be more engaged. Empirical results have revealed that entrepreneurial leader behavior produces a positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior.(Akbari et al., 2021; Bagheri & Harrison, 2020) and that work engagement has a positive impact on Innovative Work Behavior(Agarwal, 2014b; Garg & Dhar, 2017; Montani et al., 2020). The arguments and findings issued by these academics and researchers provide high-quality information that concludes that there is a relationship between Entrepreneurial Leadership, work engagement, and Innovative Work Behavior.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the analysis of the research and discussion that has been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Proactive Personality has a positive and significant effect on work engagement.
2. Proactive Personality has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior.
3. Work engagement has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior.
4. Entrepreneurial Leadership has a positive and significant effect on work engagement.
5. Entrepreneurial Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior.
6. Work engagement mediates the effect of Proactive Personality on Innovative Work Behavior. Furthermore, the form of mediation is complementary mediation in the form of partial mediation.
7. Work engagement mediates the effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior. Furthermore, the form of mediation is complementary mediation in the form of partial mediation.

Based on the results of this study, the researcher has several suggestions as follows:

For Civil Service Apparatus of the Cooperatives Service in West Sumatra; In terms of proactive personality, we must be able to improve more excellence in identifying opportunities. This is because the opportunities that employees have are only job level increases or job promotions that are determined by one of them through the

last education they have, so that employees can make adjustments to improve this by following education and training as well as adding education if possible.

a. In terms of Entrepreneurial Leadership, it must be able to improve the ability to often come up with truly new service ideas that the organization can provide and improve the ability to provide creative solutions to problems in their work, at the same time if there are activities for training and developing employee skills, it is expected that employees will participate in these activities in order to get information related to ideas or creative solutions to things that must be done in connection with their work.

b. In terms of work engagement, it is expected to be able to increase vigor in working by making adjustments to the work environment so as to create the strength to complete work well and at the same time increase the desire to go to work every day.

For work unit of the Cooperatives Service in West Sumatra;

a. In terms of Proactive Personality, we must pay more attention to job categories and job promotions that employees can have so that employees can improve their skills. excel in identifying opportunities, by way of, if possible, granting permission to increase the level of education possessed by granting permission for study while working.

b. In terms of Entrepreneurial Leadership must provide more opportunities for employee participation to be able to put forward ideas related to new services that can be provided by the organization as well as put forward creative solutions to work problems in the form of accommodating all ideas and creative solutions and then considering them to be able to choose which one to implement.

c. In terms of work engagement, we pay more attention to how to increase employee work vigor by paying attention to the condition of the employee's work environment, whether it is running well to carry out work routines so that employees are enthusiastic about working, not only to fulfill their status as State Civil Apparatus employees, but also to want to stay in the agency because of the main tasks and functions of responsibility given to them.

For further researchers;

a. Further research is expected to add other variables that influence Innovative Work Behavior by using the same or different objects.

b. Further research can also expand the scope of the research object area to more than one region outside West Sumatra.

c. This research will continue to increase the number of samples in the future so that the research results will be better.

REFERENCES

Afsar, B., Al-Ghazali, B. M., Cheema, S., & Javed, F. (2020). Cultural intelligence and innovative work behavior: the role of work engagement and interpersonal trust. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, Emerald Publishing Limited, 24(4), 1082–1109.

Agarwal, U. A. (2014a). Examining the impact of social exchange relationships on innovative work behaviour: Role of work engagement. *Team Performance Management*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 20(3–4), 102–120.

- Agarwal, U. A. (2014b). Linking justice, trust and innovative work behaviour to work engagement. *Personnel Review*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 43(1), 41–73.
- Agarwal, U. A., Datta, S., Blake-Beard, S., & Bhargava, S. (2012). Linking LMX, innovative work behaviour and turnover intentions: The mediating role of work engagement. *Career Development International*, 17(3), 208–230.
- Akbari, M., Bagheri, A., Imani, S., & Asadnezhad, M. (2021). Does entrepreneurial leadership encourage innovation work behavior? The mediating role of creative self-efficacy and support for innovation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(1), 1–22.
- Al Mehrzi, N., & Singh, S. K. (2016). Competing through employee engagement: a proposed framework. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 65(6), 831–843.
- Bagheri, A., Akbari, M., & Artang, A. (2022). How does entrepreneurial leadership affect innovation work behavior? The mediating role of individual and team creativity self-efficacy. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 25(1), 1–18.
- Bagheri, A., & Harrison, C. (2020). Entrepreneurial leadership measurement: a multi-dimensional construct. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 27(4), 659–679.
- Bai, Y., Wang, Z., Alam, M., Gul, F., & Wang, Y. (2022). The Impact of Authentic Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior: Mediating Roles of Proactive Personality and Employee Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13(June).
- Bakker, A. B., & Albrecht, S. (2018). Work engagement: current trends. *Career Development International*, 23(1), 4–11.
- Bakker, A. B., Tims, M., & Derks, D. (2012). Proactive personality and job performance: The role of job crafting and work engagement. *Human Relations*, 65(10), 1359–1378.
- Bergeron, D. M., Schroeder, T. D., & Martinez, H. A. (2014). Proactive Personality at Work: Seeing More to Do and Doing More? *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 29(1), 71–86.
- Bos-Nehles, A., Bondarouk, T., & Nijenhuis, K. (2017). Innovative work behaviour in knowledge-intensive public sector organizations: the case of supervisors in the Netherlands fire services. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 28(2), 379–398.
- Buil, I., Martínez, E., & Matute, J. (2019). Transformational leadership and employee performance: The role of identification, engagement and proactive personality. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77, 64–75.

- Cai, D., Cai, Y., Sun, Y., & Ma, J. (2018). Linking empowering leadership and employee work engagement: The effects of person-job fit, person-group fit, and proactive personality. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9(July), 1–12.
- Cai, W., Lysova, E. I., Khapova, S. N., & Bossink, B. A. G. (2019). Does Entrepreneurial Leadership Foster Creativity Among Employees and Teams? The Mediating Role of Creative Efficacy Beliefs. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 34(2), 203–217.
- Chong, S., Dyne, V. L., Kim, Y. J., & Oh, J. K. (2021). Drive and Direction: Empathy with Intended Targets Moderates the Proactive Personality–Job Performance Relationship via Work Engagement. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 70(2), 576–605.
- De Jong, J., & Den Hartog, D. (2010). Measuring innovative work behaviour. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 19(1), 23–36.